

Report on Access to Networks

Project title: **Enhancing Research and Innovation Synergies for Schools of Economics and Business**

Project no. 101159106 — RIS4SEB

D2.2 Report on Access to Networks (due in M8)

Start date of project: June 1, 2024; duration of project: 36 months

Reporting period 1: M1 – M15 (15 months), Reporting period 2: M16 – M36 (21 months)

Work package:	WP1 Enhanced internationalization and efficient use of infrastructure
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Due date:	January 31, 2025
Delivery date:	January 31, 2025
Version:	3

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Executive Summary

The **D2.2 Report on Access to Networks** is a **living document** that supports **RIS4SEB partners** in identifying and leveraging networking opportunities for **international collaboration, funding acquisition, and research capacity-building**. It provides a structured overview of:

1. **Horizon Europe Brokerage and Networking Events** – A curated selection of upcoming events. Given that many events are announced only months in advance, this section will be **continuously updated** to guide RIS4SEB partners in selecting **strategic opportunities for participation**.
2. **Research Networks and Associations** – A mapping of **key European and international research networks** that enable RIS4SEB institutions to **expand long-term collaborations, access research funding, and strengthen global engagement**. This section also includes an **analysis of institutional membership opportunities**, identifying networks such as **Crowdhelix, ABIS, CEEMAN, and EIASM** as potential platforms for **Horizon Europe project matchmaking and strategic policy engagement**.

The **widening partners**—**Prague University of Economics and Business (VŠE), Estonian Business School (EBS), and Kaunas University of Technology (KTU SEB)**—are already engaged in multiple **international networks**. These memberships provide a **strong foundation for further collaboration**, while RIS4SEB aims to **enhance participation in strategic institutional networks to maximize research impact and funding success**.

This report will serve as a **decision-making tool for travel planning**, particularly for **widening partners**, who are expected to **attend two brokerage events or relevant seminars**. It will be **updated at M12** to incorporate:

- **Newly announced brokerage events and networking opportunities.**
- **Additional relevant research networks, if applicable.**
- **Refined recommendations for institutional engagement.**

By taking a **proactive and strategic approach to network participation**, RIS4SEB institutions can **enhance international visibility, improve research competitiveness, and maximize funding opportunities within the ERA**.

1 Introduction

International collaboration is a key driver of research excellence, capacity building, and funding success. The **RIS4SEB project**, through **Work Package 2: Enhanced Internationalization and Efficient Use of Infrastructure**, aims to **strengthen institutional networks, improve access to research infrastructure, and support widening partners in establishing a stronger presence in European and international research ecosystems.**

This report is designed as a strategic **guidance tool** to assist RIS4SEB partners in identifying and selecting **the most relevant brokerage events and research networks** for participation. It is structured into two main sections:

- **Horizon Europe Brokerage and Networking Events** – This section presents a selection of upcoming brokerage and networking events under **Horizon Europe** and other European funding programs. Since many of these events are announced only a few months in advance, this list will be **regularly updated**, ensuring that RIS4SEB partners can adapt their participation strategy based on new opportunities. The document will be consulted throughout the project to inform **strategic travel decisions for widening partners**, maximizing the impact of their international engagement.
- **Research Networks and Associations** – This section provides a **comprehensive overview of relevant research networks and associations** that RIS4SEB institutions may consider joining. These networks offer opportunities for long-term collaboration, participation in funding consortia, and knowledge exchange in the fields of business, management, and economics and other related fields.

This report will also serve as a **decision-making tool for travel planning**, particularly for widening partners, who are expected to attend **two brokerage events or relevant seminars**. Given the evolving nature of networking opportunities, this document is a **living resource** that will be **regularly updated** to ensure that RIS4SEB consortium members can **select the most strategic events for participation.**

1.1 Existing Network Participation of Widening Institutions

The RIS4SEB widening partners—**Prague University of Economics and Business (VŠE)**, **Estonian Business School (EBS)**, and **Kaunas University of Technology (KTU)**—are already engaged in several **international research networks and alliances**. Understanding these existing memberships helps identify **synergies, leverage institutional connections, and strategically enhance collaboration** through RIS4SEB.

Prague University of Economics and Business (VŠE)

VŠE is a **member of the Crowdhelix network**, a global platform connecting researchers for **Horizon Europe projects**. Additionally, it participates in:

- **CEMS (Global Alliance in Management Education), PIM (Partnership in International Management), and PRME**—enhancing business education and responsible management practices.
- **CESEENet (Central, East and South-East European PhD Network)**—strengthening PhD cooperation in economics and business.

- **CESNET**—providing ICT infrastructure for research collaboration.

Estonian Business School (EBS)

As Estonia's only private, non-profit business university, EBS plays a vital role in the regional research ecosystem, with faculty actively engaged in:

- **Baltic Management Development Association and Baltic Economics Association**—regional economic and business research.
- **Baltic University Programme** - is one of the largest university cooperation's in the world, with more than 110 participating universities in the Baltic Sea Region, cooperating for education and research in Sustainable Development and Democracy.
- **EUonAIR** – new European University Association dedicated to Artificial Intelligence
- **Horizon Europe, COST, Erasmus+, and Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions**—supporting international research funding applications.

Kaunas University of Technology (KTU SEB)

KTU SEB is a **member of the European Consortium of Innovative Universities (ECIU)**, which promotes challenge-based learning and research collaboration in **energy, sustainability, and circular economy**. The institution is also involved in:

- **The ECIU Research & Innovation Hub**, connecting researchers across Europe.
- **Specialized networks** such as AIB, EURAM, EGOS, EMAC, and NMSBA.

1.2 Strengthening Institutional Networking Strategies

Building on these existing networks, RIS4SEB aims to **expand participation in Horizon Europe matchmaking platforms (e.g., Crowdhelix), enhance funding access, and leverage institutional memberships for policy engagement**. Aligning current and future memberships with RIS4SEB's objectives will **maximize collaboration opportunities, strengthen institutional visibility, and increase research funding success** within the European Research Area.

2. Horizon Europe Brokerage and Networking Events

2.1 Overview

Engaging in **brokerage and networking events** is a strategic priority for the **RIS4SEB project**, as it provides a direct avenue for **international partnerships, funding opportunities, and research visibility** within the **European Research Area (ERA)**. These events serve as platforms where RIS4SEB partners can:

- connect with potential research collaborators and consortia,
- identify upcoming Horizon Europe funding opportunities,
- and strengthen institutional networks within key research fields.

Dates and agenda of brokerage events for the presentations of Horizon Europe 2025 call for proposals under relevant clusters are not available considering that the AWP2025 has not been published yet. Therefore, **this section will be regularly reviewed and updated to ensure that RIS4SEB partners can select the most relevant and high-impact events.**

2.2 List of upcoming Horizon Europe Brokerage and Networking Events

The following table presents a **comprehensive list of upcoming brokerage and networking events /and or conferences** that potentially align with RIS4SEB's objectives. Each event has been categorized based on its **thematic relevance**, ensuring that partners can **prioritize their participation strategically**. Most relevant events are color marked.

Date	Event Name	Location	Relevance to RIS4SEB
31 Jan 2025	MSCA Lunchtime Conversation: Digital Democracy & Citizenship	Online	Relevant for media literacy and combating disinformation.
13 Feb 2025	Clean Aviation PITCH-ATHLON: Pitch & Connect	Brussels (BE)	Relevant for sustainability in aviation and innovation.
18 Feb 2025	Horizon Europe Work Programme 2025 EMMC Brokerage Event	Online	Beneficial for materials science and Horizon Europe applicants.
18-19 Feb 2025	ECS Brokerage Event 2025	Brussels (BE)	Crucial for digital innovation and R&D stakeholders.
25 Feb 2025	Open and Secure: How to Valorise your research results in an uncertain global environment?	Online	Important for maximizing research impact globally.
26 Feb 2025	European Defence Fund Industry & Matchmaking Day - Space4Defence 2025	Luxembourg	Key for defense and space technology professionals.
3-7 March 2025	European Ocean Days	Brussels (BE)	Important for marine research and environmental policy.
4-6 March 2025	New European Bauhaus Sustainable Development Environmental Policy	Erfurt (DE)	Crucial for those in sustainability and environmental policy.
6-7 March 2025	Successful R&I in Europe 2025: 12th European Networking Event	Düsseldorf (DE)	Essential for broad research and innovation networking.
25 March 2025	Horizon Europe Cluster 6 & EU Missions Matchmaking Event	Metz (FR)	Key for institutions working on Horizon Europe Cluster 6.

31 Mar – 1 Apr 2025	Global Multistakeholder High-Level Conference on Web 4.0 and Virtual Worlds	Brussels (BE)	Relevant for digital governance, AI, and emerging technologies.
8-10 April 2025	5th EMMC International Workshop: Accelerated Innovation & Sustainability	Vienna (AT)	Important for materials modelling and data ecosystems.
13-14 May 2025	Horizon Europe Info Days - Cluster 4	Online	Covers funding opportunities in Horizon Europe Cluster 4.
6-7 May 2025	SMI2G 2025, Security Research	Paris (FR)	Key for those working on security-related topics.
27-29 Aug 2025	Heritage in Depopulated European Areas	Prague (CZ)	Relevant for sustainability research in rural communities.

2.3 Additional Networking Opportunities

In addition to structured events, RIS4SEB partners can engage in **ongoing networking activities** through the [Horizon Europe Cluster 2 Community Platform](#), which facilitates virtual matchmaking and joint proposal discussions. Due to the nature of research done at the RIS4SEB consortium members, it is **highly recommended that this platform is well-communicated inside the institutions**.

Partners are encouraged to **monitor their national Horizon Europe National Contact Point (NCP) websites** and the **NCP WIDERA.NET platform** for new brokerage and networking opportunities.

2.4 Continuous Monitoring and Updates

This document is a **living resource**, and the event list will be **continuously updated** to reflect new opportunities as they arise.

The next update is planned for **M12**, incorporating:

- newly announced brokerage events for Summer and Fall 2025
- and refined strategic recommendations for participation.

RIS4SEB partners are encouraged to **consult this document periodically** to ensure that their travel and networking activities align with their research priorities and institutional goals.

3. Research Networks and Associations

3.1 Overview

Participation in **research networks and professional associations** is essential for RIS4SEB partners to **expand collaboration opportunities, increase institutional visibility, and strengthen international research capacity**. These networks provide access to **joint research initiatives, funding opportunities, and interdisciplinary knowledge exchange**, thereby enhancing integration into the **European Research Area (ERA)**.

This section presents a **comprehensive mapping** of key **research networks, academic associations, and European research platforms**, categorized based on their **thematic focus and membership structures**. Given that many networks evolve and expand, this list will be **continuously updated** to include emerging partnerships and (possibly) newly relevant associations.

3.2 Research Networks and Academic Associations

Most **field-specific research networks and associations** in **business, management, and economics** primarily offer **individual membership** options. However, there are select organizations that provide **institutional membership**, which may be **strategically beneficial for RIS4SEB institutions**.

The following table provides an **overview of relevant research networks and associations**, their **core focus areas**, and **membership types** to guide RIS4SEB partners in selecting suitable engagement opportunities. Most of the networks / associations have dedicated events, programmes or summer schools for doctoral students which represent further opportunity for networking and will be also monitored. Institutional networks are color marked. Networks / associations with individual membership will be promoted inside the widening institutions among researchers to help with their efforts to integrate in ERA on an individual basis.

Network / Association ¹	Focus Area	Membership Type	Relevance to RIS4SEB
Academy of Business in Society (ABIS)	Sustainability & Business Education	Institutional	Bridges business education with sustainable development.
Academy of International Business (AIB)	International Business Research	Individual & Institutional	Promotes impactful research in international business.
Academy of Management (AOM)	Management & Organizational Studies	Individual	Leading global association for management scholars.
European Academy of Management (EURAM)	Management Science & Business Research	Individual	Advances academic research in management.
European Accounting Association (EAA)	Accounting & Finance Research	Individual	Connects European accounting scholars and professionals.
European Association of Work and Organizational Psychology (EAWOP)	Work & Organizational Psychology	Individual & Associations	Supports applied research in workplace psychology.

¹ More detailed information about the respective associations and networks can be found in Appendix 2.

European Association for Evolutionary Political Economy (EAEPE)	Institutional and evolutionary political economy	Individual	Bridges economic theory and economic policy.
European Business History Association (EBHA)	Business History & Management Evolution	Individual	Researches the historical development of business.
European Council for Small Business and Entrepreneurship (ECSB)	Entrepreneurship & SMEs	Individual	Facilitates knowledge exchange on entrepreneurship.
European Doctoral Programmes Association in Management & Business (EDAMBA)	Doctoral Education & Research	Institutional	Strengthens doctoral education and research collaboration.
European Economic Association (EEA)	Economics Research & Policy	Individual	Fosters economic science development and policy engagement.
European Finance Association (EFA)	Financial Management & Theory	Individual	Connects finance academics and practitioners.
European Group for Organizational Studies (EGOS)	Organizational Studies & Business Strategy	Individual	Promotes interdisciplinary research on organizations.
European Institute for Advanced Studies in Management (EIASM)	Management Science & Research Networks	Institutional	Hosts academic workshops and conferences in management.
European International Business Academy (EIBA)	International Business & Global Trade	Individual	Supports research in international trade and globalization.
European Marketing Academy (EMAC)	Marketing Theory & Research	Individual	Focuses on marketing education and knowledge exchange.
European Public Choice Society (EPCS)	Political Economy & Policy Analysis	Individual	Studies non-market decision-making and public policy.
International Association for Management Development (CEEMAN)	Business & Management Development	Individual & Institutional	Supports management education and innovation.
International Family Enterprise Research Academy (IFERA)	Family Business Research & Development	Individual	Promotes research and collaboration in family enterprises.
Society for Institutional & Organizational Economics (SIOE)	Institutional & Organizational Economics	Individual	Encourages theoretical and empirical research on institutions and organizations.
Strategic Management Society (SMS)	Strategic Management & Business Strategy	Individual	Advances the study of corporate and competitive strategy.

3.3 European Research Platforms and Collaborative Networks

Beyond professional associations, RIS4SEB institutions can engage with **EU-supported research platforms and networks** that foster **international collaboration and interdisciplinary research**. These initiatives provide strategic opportunities for participation in **Horizon Europe-funded projects, policy engagement, and knowledge exchange**.

The following table outlines key **European research infrastructures, thematic collaboration platforms, and financial research networks**, including those led by the **European Central Bank (ECB)**, which contribute to economic policy, financial stability, and macroeconomic research.

Platform / Network	Focus Area	Relevance to RIS4SEB
New European Bauhaus Lab & Partner Network	Innovation & Sustainability in Urban Development	Fosters research collaboration in sustainable and creative economies.
European Digital Innovation Hubs (SmartHealth Network)	Digital Transformation in Healthcare	Facilitates digitalization and health technology research.
Circular Cities and Regions Initiative (CCRI)	Circular Economy & Sustainable Urban Development	Supports green innovation in cities and regional planning.
CrowdHelix network	All-encompassing, divided into respective helixes by topics	Networking and match-making for future project proposals.
European Construction & Technology Platform (ECTP)	Sustainable Infrastructure & Built Environment	Connects researchers in engineering, construction, and urban policy.
European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science (E-RIHS)	Cultural Heritage & Preservation Science	Strengthens research in cultural heritage conservation.
EIT Knowledge and Innovation Communities (KICs)²	Cross-sectoral Innovation & Research	Provides access to funding, training, and networks in multiple sectors.
European Central Bank (ECB) Research Networks	Economic & Financial Research	Coordinates research on macroeconomic trends, financial stability, and inflation dynamics.

The **European Central Bank (ECB) Research Networks** facilitate academic collaboration on **monetary policy, financial integration, and economic stability**. Key networks include:

- [Euro Area Business Cycle Network \(EABCN\)](#) – Focuses on macroeconomic fluctuations and business cycles.
- [Competitiveness Research Network \(CompNet\)](#) – Analyzes productivity, competitiveness, and firm dynamics.
- [Macro-prudential Research Network \(MaRs\)](#) – Studies financial stability and systemic risk.
- [Household Finance and Consumption Network \(HFCN\)](#) – Examines household financial behavior and economic well-being.

² More detailed information about the EIT KIC communities can be found in Appendix 3.

- [Price-setting Microdata Analysis Network \(PRISMA\)](#) – Investigates inflation trends and price-setting mechanisms.

Participation in these platforms and networks provides **access to cutting-edge research, policy discussions, and funding opportunities**. RIS4SEB institutions are encouraged to **monitor new developments and engage in relevant initiatives to strengthen their research impact at the European level**.

3.4 Strategic Engagement and Continuous Monitoring

To **maximize impact and engagement**, RIS4SEB partners are encouraged to:

- **assess the strategic value** of joining each network based on institutional priorities,
- **monitor new membership opportunities** and EU-funded research collaborations
- **engage actively in relevant events, working groups, and funding initiatives** within these networks.

This structured approach will ensure that **RIS4SEB institutions remain well-positioned** within the evolving European research landscape, enabling sustained **international collaboration, funding acquisition, and institutional growth**.

3.5 Strategic Analysis of Institutional Membership Networks

Institutional memberships in research networks provide RIS4SEB partners with long-term opportunities to **enhance collaboration, participate in funding consortia, and strengthen visibility within European research frameworks**. While many networks in business, management, and economics offer only individual memberships, a select number of organizations allow institutional participation, presenting strategic value in alignment with Horizon Europe priorities (Appendix 1).

Networks Supporting Sustainability and Business Innovation

For institutions aiming to strengthen their position in **sustainability and circular economy research**, the **Academy of Business in Society (ABIS)** is particularly relevant. It connects business schools with sustainability initiatives and aligns with **Horizon Europe’s New European Bauhaus and Circular Cities and Regions Initiative**. Membership in ABIS facilitates direct engagement in policy discussions on sustainable business education and corporate responsibility.

Similarly, **CEEMAN (International Association for Management Development in Dynamic Societies)** offers institutions a platform for business education innovation and aligns with **Horizon Europe’s goals in industrial competitiveness and inclusive growth**. Through CEEMAN, institutions can gain access to best practices in management education, enhancing their relevance in research-driven capacity-building initiatives.

Strengthening Research Collaboration and Doctoral Education

Institutional participation in **EIASM (European Institute for Advanced Studies in Management)** is strategically beneficial for RIS4SEB institutions seeking to engage in **collaborative research in management and digital transformation**. EIASM provides structured networking opportunities with

leading management scholars and hosts specialized academic workshops, directly supporting research capacity-building efforts.

For institutions with a **focus on doctoral education and researcher training**, the **European Doctoral Programmes Association in Management & Business (EDAMBA)** is a key network. It enables universities to develop **joint doctoral training programs**, aligns with **Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions (MSCA)** under Horizon Europe, and supports mobility programs for early-stage researchers.

Facilitating Horizon Europe Project Matchmaking

Beyond thematic research networks, **Crowdhelix** presents a distinct opportunity for RIS4SEB institutions by offering a **structured matchmaking platform for Horizon Europe project consortia**. This network allows institutions to connect with relevant research teams across Europe based on **specific Horizon Europe calls**. By actively engaging in CrowdHelix, RIS4SEB partners can identify **funding opportunities, build consortia, and secure project partnerships**, thereby enhancing their chances of successfully coordinating or participating in Horizon Europe-funded initiatives.

Strategic Guidelines for RIS4SEB Institutions

To maximize the benefits of institutional membership, RIS4SEB partners should:

1. **Strategically select networks based on research priorities and funding alignment** – ABIS and CEEMAN provide direct access to sustainability and business development networks, while EIASM and EDAMBA offer structured academic research collaboration opportunities.
2. **Leverage institutional memberships to strengthen Horizon Europe applications** – Engaging with CrowdHelix can facilitate successful funding applications and increase research visibility in European funding frameworks.
3. **Participate actively in policy discussions and research working groups** – Institutional engagement in ABIS and CEEMAN ensures visibility in EU policy dialogues related to sustainability, business education, and research funding priorities.

By strategically integrating these networks into their internationalization strategies, RIS4SEB institutions can **enhance collaboration, secure funding, and expand their role in European research initiatives** and enlarge their networks.

4 Conclusion

The **D2.2 Report on Access to Networks** serves as a **strategic resource** for RIS4SEB partners, guiding their engagement in **brokerage events, research networks, and institutional collaborations**. By systematically mapping **existing and potential networking opportunities**, this document supports RIS4SEB's goal of **strengthening internationalization, enhancing research visibility, and maximizing participation in the European Research Area (ERA)**.

Key Takeaways:

1. **Leveraging Brokerage Events for Strategic Collaboration**
 - Horizon Europe brokerage events provide **direct access to research consortia, funding opportunities, and policy discussions**.
 - Widening partners are encouraged to **prioritize participation based on institutional research priorities** and potential funding alignment.
2. **Strengthening Institutional Memberships**
 - RIS4SEB partners are already members of key **international networks**, including **CEMS, ECIU, CESEENet, and Crowdhelix**, which serve as **foundations for further collaboration**.
 - Expanding institutional memberships in networks such as **Crowdhelix, ABIS, CEEMAN, and EIASM** can further **facilitate Horizon Europe funding applications and policy engagement**.

Next Steps and Continuous Monitoring

As **networking opportunities and funding programs evolve**, this document will be **regularly updated** to reflect **new brokerage events, emerging research networks, and refined institutional strategies**.

The next update, planned for **M12**, will incorporate:

- Newly announced **Horizon Europe brokerage events for Summer and Fall 2025**.
- Additional **research networks and associations** relevant to RIS4SEB's strategic priorities, if applicable.
- Refined **recommendations on institutional membership and engagement strategies**.

By maintaining a **flexible and responsive approach to network participation**, RIS4SEB partners can **maximize their impact within the European Research Area and beyond**, ensuring **sustainable collaboration, increased funding opportunities, and enhanced research capacity**.

Appendix 1: Relevant clusters, missions and initiatives under Horizon Europe as identified for the RIS4SEB partners

In synergy with Task 2.1- Joint internationalization strategy for R&I, a preliminary assessment of the high potential areas for joint R&I projects development has been carried out. Such high-level areas of interest have been matched with Horizon Europe strategic plan 2025-2027 identifying relevant Clusters and destinations and related partnerships and initiatives of interest. The outcomes are reported in the table below.

Health	Culture/creativity/society	Industrial competitiveness	Smart City/Public spaces
<p>Cluster 1 – Health</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Destination 1 – Staying healthy in a rapidly changing society • Destination 2 – Living and working in a health-promoting environment • Destination 3 – Tackling diseases and reducing disease burden • Destination 4 – Ensuring access to innovative, sustainable and high-quality healthcare <p>Cross-cutting & others</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mission Cancer • EIT KIC Health • Innovative Health Initiative (IHI) PPP 	<p>Cluster 2 – Culture, Creativity and Inclusive society</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Destination 1– Innovative Research on Democracy and Governance • Destination 2 – Innovative research on European cultural heritage and cultural and creative industries • Destination 3 – Innovative research on social and economic transformations. <p>Cross-cutting & others</p> <p>New European Bauhaus EIT KIC Culture</p>	<p>Cluster 4 – Digital, Industry & Space</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Destination 4 – Digital & Emerging Technologies for Competitiveness and Fit for the Green Deal • Destination 6 – A human-centred and ethical development of digital and industrial technologies <p>Cluster 6 – Food & circular (bio)economy</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Destination 3 – Circular Economy & Bioeconomy <p>Cross-cutting & others</p> <p>EIT KIC Digital EIT KIC Manufacturing</p>	<p>Cluster 5 – Energy</p> <p>Destination 4 – Efficient, sustainable and inclusive energy use</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Built4People Partnership <p>Cluster 6 – Food & circular (bio)economy</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Destination 3 – Circular Economy & Bioeconomy • Destination 6 –Resilient, inclusive, healthy and green rural, coastal and urban communities <p>Cross-cutting & others</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New European Bauhaus • Mission Climate Neutral & Smart Cities • Mission Adaptation to Climate Change • Circular Cities and Regions Initiative EIT KIC Climate EIT KIC Urban Mobility

Appendix 2: List of field-specific research networks and associations in business/management and economics with descriptions

Academy of Business in Society (ABIS) is a global network of companies and academic institutions whose expertise, commitment and resources are leveraged to invest in a more sustainable future for business in society. Its mission is to bridge business and business education towards systemic change and sustainable development. To reach this goal, they contribute to the debate and the practice involved in equipping current and future business leaders with the knowledge, skills, and capabilities for the long-term success of business in society. Only institutional membership is available. More information is available [here](#).

Academy of International Business (AIB) was founded in 1959 by a close-knit group of like-minded scholars looking to share the ideas and resources that would help define the emerging field of international business. Today, it is a 501(c)(3) nonprofit dedicated to promoting impactful research, improving business education and practice, and collaborating with leaders in policy and interdisciplinary research. Both individual and institutional memberships are possible. More information is available [here](#).

Academy of Management (AOM) is the preeminent professional association for management and organization scholars. Its worldwide members are professors and PhD students in business schools at universities, academics in related social science and other fields, and practitioners who value knowledge creation and application. Founded in 1936, its global community today is nearly 18,000 strong and spans over 120 countries. Only individual membership is possible. More information is available [here](#).

European Academy of Management (EURAM) is a learned society founded in 2001. It aims at advancing the academic field of management in Europe. With members from 60 countries in Europe and beyond, EURAM has a high degree of diversity and provides its members with opportunities to enrich debates over a variety of research management themes and traditions. Only individual membership is possible. More information is available [here](#).

European Accounting Association (EAA) is an academic association that supports high-quality accounting research, teaching and knowledge exchange with practice by providing a platform that enables accounting academics to develop themselves and benefit society through its activities. It also aims at the development of relations with all other professional and research-oriented Associations which are active in the field of accounting, as well as with European or international committees and authorities concerned with political decision making in this field. The EAA has established a secure and developing series of networks that bring together all accounting researchers interested in a wider European concept of its subject and research interests. Only individual membership is possible. More information is available [here](#).

European Association for Evolutionary Political Economy (EAEPE) is a pluralist forum of social scientists that brings together institutional and evolutionary economists broadly defined. EAEPE members are scholars working on realistic approaches to economic theory and economic policy. EAEPE's research is organised around Research Areas (RAs) that include: Methodology of economics (A), Economic sociology (B), Institutional change (C), Innovation and technological change (D), Industrial Policy and Development (E1), Entrepreneurship and Theory of the Firm (E2), Environment-economy interactions (F), Macroeconomic regulation and Institutions (G), Effective Demand, Income Distribution and Finance (H), Comparative Political Economy (I), Monetary economics, finance and financial institutions (J), Gender economics and social identity (K), Labour economics (L), Social economics (M), Human development and institutions (N), Territory and

migration (O), Economic history (P), Evolutionary economic simulations (S), History of political economy (T), Conceptions of Evolutionary Political Economy (V), Global political economy (W), Networks (X), Co-operative economy and collective ownership (Z). Only individual membership is possible. More information is available [here](#).

European Association of Work and Organizational Psychology (EAWOP) mission is to promote and support the development and application of Work and Organizational Psychology in Europe and to facilitate links between scientists and practitioners working in this field across Europe. EAWOP has been designed as an open network in which associations (called ‘Constituents’) as well as individual members can participate. Associations – in many cases ‘sections’ or ‘divisions’ of national psychological associations – are expected to play a crucial role in EAWOP by opening some of their activities to EAWOP members from other countries, and by cooperating with other associations in so-called ‘Dedicated Networks’ related to particular issues relevant for W&O psychology. Associations may also organize special activities in cooperation with other associations and/or the EAWOP secretariat. Individuals can take part as members of Constituents, i.e. through a collective arrangement, or on a direct, personal basis. Only individual membership is possible. More information is available [here](#).

European Business History Association (EBHA) was established at the end of 1994 as the professional body for individuals interested in the development of business and management in Europe from the earliest time to the present day. Only individual membership is possible. More information is available [here](#).

European Central Bank (ECB) leads and coordinates research through a number of networks in order to obtain insights that support its decision-making. These include the following:

- [Capital Markets and Financial Integration in Europe Network](#)
- [Challenges for Monetary Policy Transmission in a Changing World \(ChaMP\) Research Network](#)
- [Competitiveness Research Network \(CompNet\)](#)
- [Euro Area Business Cycle Network \(EABCN\)](#)
- [Eurosysteem Research Network on Cash \(EURECA\)](#)
- [Expert group studying the causes of low inflation \(LIFT\)](#)
- [Household Finance and Consumption Network \(HFCN\)](#)
- [Inflation Persistence Network \(IPN\)](#)
- [International Linkages and Spill-overs Network \(Intlink\)](#)
- [Macro-prudential Research Network \(MaRs\)](#)
- [Price-setting Microdata Analysis Network \(PRISMA\)](#)
- [Research Task Force on monetary policy, macroprudential policy and financial stability \(RTF\)](#)
- [Wage Dynamics Network \(WDN\)](#)

European Council for Small Business and Entrepreneurship (ECSB) is a research-driven non-profit organisation. Its main objective is to facilitate the creation and dissemination of new knowledge through research and the open exchange of ideas between academia, education, policy and practice. Only individual membership is possible. More information is available [here](#).

European Doctoral Programmes Association in Management & Business Administration (EDAMBA) is an international non-profit association currently operating in 28 countries. Its mission is to develop common ideas, values, evaluation criteria, standards, and practices to assess and enhance the quality of doctoral education, through the exchange of experiences and cooperation in a global network. EDAMBA members are committed to creating and sharing initiatives and achieving excellence whilst

appreciating and promoting collaboration, diversity and community building. Only individual membership is possible. More information is available [here](#).

[European Economic Association \(EEA\)](#) is an International scientific body, with membership open to all persons involved or interested in economics, that promotes the development of economic science throughout Europe, as well as communication between educators, researchers and students, the links between university and research centres and relations between academic economists and policy-makers. Only individual membership is possible. More information is available [here](#).

[European Finance Association \(EFA\)](#) was created in 1974 under the auspices of the European Foundation for Management Development (EFMD) and in close cooperation with the European Institute for Advanced Studies in Management (EIASM). EFA's mission is to foster a professional society for academics, practitioners, and doctoral students in the greater field of Finance, who are interested in research areas such as financial management and financial theory along with their applications. EFA serves its community of members based in Europe and elsewhere in the world as an evolving professional network for the exchange of ideas, expertise, news and knowledge in Finance at the international level. Only individual membership is possible. More information is available [here](#).

[European Group for Organizational Studies \(EGOS\)](#) is a scholarly association which aims to further the theoretical and/or empirical advancement of knowledge about organizations, organizing and the contexts in which organizations operate. As a collective, one of its main aims is to maintain and provide a voice for the critical and analytical approaches of its members to the study of organization worldwide. Only individual membership is possible. More information is available [here](#).

[European Institute for Advanced Studies in Management \(EIASM\)](#) is an international network for management research and teaching that includes more than 70,000 management scientists from all over the world. In 1995 it launched its institutional members' network, EIASM's Academic Council. The main purpose of this initiative was to enable closer ties with those institutions that gain from and contribute most to the activities of EIASM, as well as to offer a forum for the exchange of information between member institutions. Another incentive to formalising the institutional membership structure was to provide an ongoing means of financial support for the annual activities of EIASM. On average, between 70 and 80 universities, research institutes or business schools are members of EIASM's Academic Council, representing some 20 European countries. Only institutional membership (at EIASM's Academic Council) is possible – more information is available [here](#).

[European International Business Academy \(EIBA\)](#) is a professional society for academics and others interested in the multidisciplinary field of International Business (IB) that serves as a community network promoting research, global communication, knowledge transfer, life-long learning and exchanges of ideas. Membership is open to individuals from Europe and elsewhere in the world. EIBA comprises about 500 members from over 50 countries. Only individual membership is possible. More information is available [here](#).

[European Marketing Academy \(EMAC\)](#) is a professional society for people involved or interested in marketing theory and research established in 1975. The purpose of the European Marketing Academy is to provide a society for persons professionally concerned with or interested in marketing theory and research. Its aims are to serve as the core of a communication network for disseminating information and promoting international exchange in the field of marketing. At present, the Academy has over 1000 members from more than 50 different countries in all five continents. Only individual membership is possible. More information is available [here](#).

[European Public Choice Society \(EPCS\)](#) aims at promoting scientific research on the economic and interdisciplinary analysis of non-market decision making processes and institutions, and to facilitate

the exchange of work and ideas about it. Only individual membership is possible. More information is available [here](#).

[International Association for Management Development in Dynamic Societies \(CEEMAN\)](#) is an international management development association established in 1993 with the aim of accelerating the growth in quality of management development in central and eastern Europe. Now it is a global network of management development institutions interested in quality of education and innovations in this field, as well as in the broad area of subjects related to change, with 200 members from 50 countries in Europe, North America, Latin America, Africa, and Asia. Both individual and institutional memberships are possible. More information is available [here](#).

[International Family Enterprise Research Academy \(IFERA\)](#) was established in 2001, is a non-profit association that encompasses an international network of academics, researchers and other family business key stakeholders, dedicated to the advancement of family business research. Only individual membership is possible. More information is available [here](#).

[Society for Institutional & Organizational Economics \(SIOE\)](#) promotes rigorous theoretical and empirical investigation of the nature, behavior, and governance of organizations and institutions. Members of the Society use approaches drawn from various disciplines, including economics, law, political science, strategy, management, organization theory, and history. Through its annual conference and other activities, SIOE provides an opportunity to engage in conversation that spans fields, regions, and generations. The Society has historically attracted a diverse community of scholars from around the world. It makes a special effort to develop and encourage capacity for junior scholars working on institutions and organizations. Only individual membership is possible. More information is available [here](#).

[Strategic Management Society \(SMS\)](#) is an organization of more than 3,000 members that is unique in bridging the worlds of reflective practice and thoughtful scholarship while supporting the development and dissemination of strategic management insights and fostering contacts and interchange around the world. Only individual membership is possible. More information is available [here](#).

Appendix 3: list of EIT KICs

There are also [EIT Knowledge and Innovation Communities](#) that RIS4SEB widening institutions can consider joining:

- **EIT KIC Climate** - <https://www.climate-kic.org/>
- **EIT KIC Culture and Creativity**- <https://eit-culture-creativity.eu/>
- **EIT KIC Digital**- <https://www.eitdigital.eu/>
- **EIT KIC Food** - <https://eithealth.eu/>
- **EIT KIC Health** - <https://eithealth.eu/>
- **EIT KIC Manufacturing** - <https://eitmanufacturing.eu/>
- **EIT KIC Raw Materials** - <https://eitrawmaterials.eu/>
- **EIT KIC Urban Mobility** - <https://eiturbanmobility.eu/>
- **EIT KIC Water** - new EIT KIC that does not have a website, yet. More information is available [here](#) and [here](#).

EIT KICs represent EU-sponsored networks that go beyond research and represent a link to EU policymaking and industry. Partners may consider joining relevant EIT KIC but should carefully evaluate the costs versus benefits - see, for instance, the price list for EIT KIC Digital [here](#).